

PRONUNCIATION DIFFICULTIES OF UZBEK SPEAKING EFL LEARNERS: A STUDY BASED ON IELTS CANDIDATES IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: *This is to investigate the reasons for the difficulties of learning pronunciation of Uzbek EFL learners with special attention to IELTS candidates and to provide students with ways to build up their pronunciation ability on part with international standard pronunciation in order to speak accurately and understand native speakers effortlessly.*

One hundred students were taken into this study from the sample region. Pronunciation difficulties of Uzbek IELTS candidates are taken to study based on four different aspects such as students' ability, interest and exposure to English, the support from home atmosphere, teachers' ability to teach pronunciation and school textbook as well as teachers' guidelines support. Data were collected both qualitatively and quantitatively by providing questionnaires with at least 200 students on a random sampling basis then conducted interviews with teachers and the data collected from the interview were analysed thematically. This study unearthed the following, IELTS candidates in Uzbekistan don't have a fear of speaking but are confident enough and motivated. The home atmosphere will not be immediately changed but as the generation changes. Teachers don't have comparatively greater challenges in teaching pronunciation yet there are some teachers who encounter a lack of ability, skills and proficiency to become a pronunciation model to IELTS learners. Besides, the availability of learning and teaching material online and physically is adequate enough to carry on the teaching of pronunciation. IELTS practice test books and teachers' guidelines help learners pronounce words well or appropriately. Apart from the availability of previous research on this topic, it could have been better for the researcher to meet at least 10 parents or relatives to have an overall idea of the impact of the home atmosphere and their contribution toward their children's learning pronunciation from home.

Keywords: *IELTS speaking, pronunciation, EFL pronunciation, Uzbek EFL learners*

Introduction

The more a learner reads the better he writes likewise, the more he listens the better he speaks. When a person knows a language, he can express thoughts either in writing or in speaking yet speaking is more natural and usual than writing. When a person attends an interview or participates in a discussion, he should be able to convey the message clearly and unequivocally. In this contemporary era, the global

villaging opens ways broader ahead to continue studies and work abroad in any part of the world. Speaking is always assessed before giving admission to any studies or employment opportunities abroad because we cannot carry a pen and a piece of paper all the time to write every conversation and read the response from the other person.

In order to carry out this scientific research reliably, aspects that thwart accurate pronunciation are seen from various angles such as learners’ side, teachers’ contribution, support from teaching modules and home environmental influences.

Pronunciation in IELTS speaking plays a crucial role, 25% of the speaking performance of an IELTS candidate depends on standard pronunciation. In which the candidate is able to use a full range of pronunciation features, maintain the range of pronunciation features throughout the session and the pronunciation must not require extra effort to understand [1].

Objective:

On the whole, the purpose of this study is to find out the reasons for the difficulties of learning pronunciation while speaking in English and to outline possible solutions in order for Uzbek EFL learners and IELTS candidates shall build up their pronunciation ability well to speak accurately and understand native speakers as they do in their L1 conversations.

Discussion:

English Standard pronunciations according to the previous research article [2] stated that Received Pronunciation (RP) and General American (GenAm). RP refers to a non-regional pronunciation found mainly in the United Kingdom, sometimes known non-technically as ‘BBC English’ or ‘the Queen’s English’. General American refers to a standardised form of North American English, often associated with broadcast journalism and, thus, sometimes known as ‘network English’.

The pronunciation is important because 527 million people speak English as their mother tongue and 2 billion people in 2050 will speak English around the globe which will then nearly be a quarter of the world’s population. Incorrect pronunciation can create a negative impression. It can further lead people to think not to communicate with you as it would be difficult and require much effort to convey their message. Inaccurate pronunciation can cause misunderstanding among speakers and it may sound rude even if you didn’t mean to be rude [3].

The challenges of teaching English pronunciation to Uzbek learners and the importance of teachers’ ability to give significance to the appropriate use of English in communication together using speech features appropriately are emphasised and further ensured the ability of Uzbek learners to speak English with a native-like proficiency [4].

Uzbekistan has been using teacher-centred, book-centred and grammar-translation techniques to teach ELF learners. Not all EFL educators in Uzbekistan are able to

teach pronunciation as there had not been any opportunity for them to develop it on par with international standards [5].

Speaking difficulties in English with accurate pronunciation among ESL students is one of the topics many scholars have already learnt about. However, during the researcher’s encounter with more than a hundred IELTS candidates in Uzbekistan, the researcher learnt that IELTS candidates have pronunciation difficulties in both vowel, diphthong and consonant sounds, and there is a need for scientific research in order to bring forth solutions to those shortcomings. This research shall dig deeper into the difficulties of Uzbek IELTS candidates’ consonantal pronunciation and the reasons for inaccurate pronunciation.

100 students were taken into this study and noticeably everyone had trouble in pronouncing consonants. Learners consider despite available online resources and learning materials, lack of family support and a supportive home atmosphere are two important reasons that hinder learners from acquiring native-like or standard pronunciation. In this era, Uzbekistan has evolved to have higher educational institutions which are abler to compete in the quality of education, infrastructure and other facilities with developed countries around the world [6].

Conclusion

Mostly, ELS learners preparing for the IELTS in Uzbekistan have difficulties in pronouncing the following sounds /h/, /θ/, /ð/, /s/, /ʃ/, /z/, /w/, /v/, /f/, (light) /l/, and /j/. Learners utter these sounds either incorrectly or in a way that phonates another sound in English. First language influence, teachers’ support and the ability of teachers to support learners learn pronunciation have been identified as major issues that hamper learners’ accurate pronunciation.

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